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DELIVERABLE 4.3

Data set of ~1 mil scRNAseq for endometrium cells at reproductive age to assess variability among individuals

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List of Acronyms

scRNAseq	Single Cell RNA sequencing	WOI	Window of Implantation	PE	Preeclampsia
HCA	Human Cell Atlas	sPE	Severe Preeclampsia	UMAP	Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection
DEGs	Differentially expressed Genes	QC	Quality Control	NGS	Next Generation Sequencing
WP	Work Package	PCA	Principal Component Analysis	HE	Healthy

1 PURPOSE OF THIS DOCUMENT

The purpose of this document is to present the first version of the “Data set of scRNAseq for health and preeclamptic endometrial cells at reproductive age to assess variability among individuals”. As part of deliverable D4.3, we will address three main areas:

- a) Acquisition and processing of healthy and preeclampsia tissue biopsies.
- b) Optimisation of the bioinformatics pipeline for the scRNAseq analysis.
- c) Preliminary results from the healthy endometrial biopsies along menstrual cycle and preeclampsia case disease.

Due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, tissue recruitment for HUTER has been greatly impacted, which has had implications for deliverable D4.3. As a result, amended delivery deadlines were agreed for WP4 so that it was re-scheduled for February 28th 2022, an extension of 6 months from the original delivery date.

This document provides a description of the rigorous experimental process for the endometrial biopsies analysis by single cell technology during this project, as well as the specific bioinformatic pipeline and an overview of the main results. This document has been developed by INCLIVA, which is the main lead partner of deliverable D4.3 in collaboration with the additional partners involved in this Work Package.

Related documents

Documents linked to current actions to be delivered:

HUTER_WP4_D4.1_ Data set of ~1 mil scRNAseq for endometrium cells across the lifespan

Documents linked to future actions to be delivered:

HUTER_WP4_D4.2_ Data set of ~1 mil scRNAseq for myometrium cells across the lifespan

HUTER_WP4_D4.4_ Whole genome sequencing for all healthy study population

HUTER_WP4_D4.5_ Report on identified new cell states and cell to cell communication mechanisms

2 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main goal of the HUTER project is to create a reference atlas of the human uterus in health and disease by utilising state-of-the-art technologies allowing transcriptome profiling (scRNA-seq), spatial organisation (spatial transcriptomics), protein profiling and epigenomic analysis. This project is aligned with the Human Cell Atlas (HCA) initiative which aims to profile all cells in the human body and is part of the “Reproductive Network”, an area of the HCA focused on.

This document describes how researchers have performed tasks to achieve the objectives of the project, being for the related Work Package 4:

- Identification of cell types and states in the endometrium, across life span for a healthy uterus.
- Identification of cell types and states in the myometrium, across life span for a healthy uterus.
- Elucidation of the effects of the menstrual cycle on the endometrial cells of fertile women.
- Identification of a plausible landscape of somatic mutations in the uterus throughout lifespan through single-cell genotype.

Specifically, the work package 4.3 is focus in:

- (i) Identification of cell types and states in the endometrium, across life span for a healthy uterus.
- (ii) Elucidation of the effects of the menstrual cycle on the endometrial cells of fertile women.
- (iii) Identification of cell types and states in the preeclampsia case study.
- (iv) Elucidation of the identification of potential molecular mechanisms underlying the endometrial pathogenesis in sPE.

We have generated scRNA-seq data from the endometrium of 38 biopsy samples distributed along the menstrual cycle. We used 100,837 good quality cells to perform integration and clustering analysis, and our preliminary results could confirm the presence of main cell types, and furthermore four cell states that could be classified associated to principal changes along with the menstrual cycle phases.

In a preeclampsia case study, we present first results in the transcriptomic atlas definition of defective decidualization at the single cell level. Data integrative analysis revealed the presence of main expected cell types: epithelium, stroma, perivascular fraction, endothelium, lymphocytes, and macrophages. Interestingly, our preliminar data reveal an imbalance in cell populations subtypes of stroma, depicting a disrupted response to decidualization stimulus in vivo. Expanding these results might allow the identification of potential molecular mechanisms underlying the uterine/endometrial pathogenesis underlying sPE.

3 INTRODUCTION

HUTER project

The HUTER project is an European pilot action to build on the foundations of the Human Cell Atlas (HCA), with the aims of generating a comprehensive reference catalogue of all human cells in order to better understand disease. HUTER is one of six pilot actions (along with BRAINTIME, DISCOVAIR, ESPACE, HCA Organoid, HUGODECA) within the Horizon2020 Research and Innovation Framework Programme, which initiated in January 2020. The HUTER projects aims to provide unprecedented insights into multiple layers of transcriptomic and spatial patterning of gene expression in the uterus, an important dynamic female organ that exhibits changes in cellular processes and identities, through not only the menstrual cycle, but also across lifespan. The endometrium, the mucosal layer of the uterus, goes through cyclic phases of regeneration, differentiation and shedding during a women's reproductive life from puberty to menopause, whilst the myometrium is the underlying layer consisting mainly of smooth muscle cells, supporting stroma and vascular tissues. The two ovarian hormones, estrogen and progesterone, intricately regulate endometrial growth and differentiation. The endometrium consists of two main layers: the basal layer, which remains attached to the myometrium in all stages of the menstrual cycle, and the functional layer, which develops during the proliferative phase and is shed during menstruation. The basal layer is thought to be enriched in progenitor cells, but the epigenetic regulation controlling expansion and differentiation remains unknown. The main goal of Work Package 4 is to sequence the endometrium at reproductive age by:

- (i) Identification of cell types and states in the endometrium, across life span for a healthy uterus.
- (ii) Elucidation of the effects of the menstrual cycle on the endometrial cells of fertile women.
- (iii) Identification of cell types and states in the preeclampsia case study.
- (iv) Elucidation of the identification of potential molecular mechanisms underlying the endometrial pathogenesis in sPE.

Healthy endometrial biopsies

Specifically, the **endometrium** is known for its remarkable regenerative capacity and extensive remodelling, with appropriate hormonal stimulus during the menstrual cycle in reproductive life, some 400 times in a lifetime. In humans, the endometrium is composed of luminal epithelium and epithelial-lined glands, surrounded by a supportive stroma with rich vascularization and the cyclic presence of non-resident immune cells. Morphologically, it can be divided into a superficial functional layer that, with each cycle (the menstrual cycle) is removed and sheds together with the basal layer, which is capable of regenerating to complete tissue.

This cyclic transformation is executed through dynamic changes in states and interactions of multiple cell types. Although different categorization schemes exist, the transformation can be primarily divided into two major phases by the event of ovulation: the proliferative (pre-ovulatory) and secretory (post-ovulatory) phase¹. During the secretory phase, the endometrium enters a narrow window of receptive state that is both structurally and biochemically ideal for embryo to implant^{2,3} i.e. the mid-secretory phase or the window of implantation (WOI). Given the broad relevance in human fertility and regenerative biology, a systematic characterization of endometrial transformation across the natural menstrual cycle has been long pursued.

Disease case: severe preeclampsia

The challenge of this project is to decipher the molecular composition of the human uterus at cellular resolution in health and disease, such as preeclampsia. Preeclampsia is one of the major obstetric complications that affects around 8% of pregnancies worldwide^{4,5,6}. This disease is characterized by high blood pressure and signs of damage to another organ system, most often liver and kidneys. Severe preeclampsia (sPE) is diagnosed based on a further elevation of blood pressure (systolic ≥ 160 mm Hg or diastolic of ≥ 100 mm Hg) or any of the following: thrombocytopenia, impaired liver function, progressive renal insufficiency, pulmonary edema and the new onset of cerebral or visual disturbances that might end in HELLP syndrome (hemolysis, elevated liver enzymes and low platelet count) and/ or eclampsia⁷. Our role in this important project is to understand the cellular atlas in the endometrium of patients who suffered severe preeclampsia in a previous pregnancy. Preeclampsia is a severe complication that if not diagnosed and treated on time, this condition can cause life-threatening consequences for both mother and child, especially in the severe cases. As a result, preeclampsia accounts for more than 76.000 maternal and 500.000 infant deaths each year. There is an important public health expenditure associated with maternal and neonatal morbidity and 30% increased risk of developing long-term diseases later in life such as cardiovascular problems.

Our published work supported by INCLIVA demonstrates the existence of a molecular defect in the uterine tissue “the endometrium” in women that had a previous pregnancy affected by preeclampsia⁸⁻¹¹. More in detail, this defect affects the process that undergoes the endometrial tissue to be prepared for an embryo implantation called decidualization. In this line, the HUTER project open the possibilities to dig on cellular mechanisms that are altered.

The Human Uterus Cell Atlas is being applied in a pathological condition to demonstrate its potency as a discovery tool in medical research. We have selected to study preeclampsia, the disease with the highest incidence during pregnancy. These results will facilitate new clinical advancements by enabling a better understanding of this pregnancy-associated problem for its early diagnosis and identification of candidate targets for therapy.

4 Experimental pipeline

Overview of experimental plan

To study molecular mechanisms in endometrial progression along menstrual cycle we have set up single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) assays to profile cells from fresh tissue samples. We have obtained 38 endometrial biopsies during all phases of the menstrual cycle from healthy fertile women and processed to single-cell suspensions, which have been submitted to RNA sequencing. We have established the bioinformatic analysis pipeline to identify multiple endometrial cell types, for which we have optimised dissociation protocols and QC filters to obtain high-quality data (Figure 1).

Based on the understanding of healthy progression of menstrual cycle at cellular level, we have also recruited preeclampsia samples and analysed potential points of alteration of decidualization. On such, we have collected endometrial biopsies during the late secretory phase of 3 healthy women and 7 women who suffered preeclampsia.

Figure 1. Overview of methodology established for scRNAseq study of human endometrium cells at reproductive age.

Processing of samples

Biopsies of endometrial tissue obtained in Estonia and Spain are immediately preserved in HypoThermosol® FRS solution (Stemcell Technologies) and sent at 4°C to Igenomix Foundation laboratory (Valencia, Spain) for its processing. The samples are treated mechanically and enzymatically to obtain single cell suspension of both epithelial and stromal fractions and processed for scRNA-seq using 10X genomics platform and NGS (Illumina). The tissue received in HypoThermosol® FRS solution are rinsed in cold PBS and minced in a petri dish on ice and sterility conditions for 10 min using scalpels. Afterwards, the sample are enzymatically digested with a solution containing 1 mg/mL Collagenase V (C9263, Sigma-Aldrich), 100 µg/mL DNase Type I (03724751103, Roche) and 10% inactivated FBS in RPMI media for 45 min at 37°C and 175 rpm. The digestion are then inactivated by adding 1 volume of 10% inactivated FBS in RPMI media (Complete medium), the solution filtered through a 100-µm cell strainer, and the strainer washed with 5 mL of complete medium. The flow-through solution contains the stromal fraction, whereas the undigested tissue retained in the cell strainer is the epithelial fraction of the endometrium.

To complete the purification and disaggregation of the stromal fraction, the single cell suspension is centrifuged 5 min at 2000 rpm, the supernatant discarded, and the pellet washed with 5mL of PBS. If the cell pellet contained blood, it is incubated with 3 mL of 1x RBC Lysis Buffer (eBioscience, ThermoFisher Scientific) 5 min at RT to eliminate blood from the sample and then diluted with 10 mL complete medium for inactivation. The cell suspension of stromal fraction is washed with PBS, centrifuged 5 min at 2000 rpm and the pellet resuspended with 200 µL of 0.04% BSA in PBS (w/v). Finally, sample are filtered using a 40-µm flowmi filter (BAH136800040-50EA, Merk) to obtain a single cell suspension of the stromal fraction.

The 100-µm cell strainer mentioned above contains the epithelial tissue. This is recovered by flushing 15 mL PBS to the inverted cell strainer into a 50-mL falcon tube and centrifuged 5 min at 2000 rpm. For digestion of the epithelial tissue fragments of endometrium, the pellet is incubated with 5 mL of 100 µg/mL DNase Type I (03724751103, Roche) in 0.25% Trypsin-EDTA solution (25200072, Life Technologies) 10 min at 37°C and 175rpm shaking. After inactivation with complete media, the suspension is filtered through a 100-µm cell strainer, the filter washed with 5 mL PBS and the solution centrifuged 5 min at 2000 rpm. If needed, the pellet will be treated with RBC lysis solution as mentioned before, washed again with PBS, resuspended with 200 µL of 0.04% BSA in PBS (w/v) and filtered using 40-µm flowmi filter.

An aliquot of stromal and epithelial cell suspensions are stained with Tripzan Blue dye and counted for alive cell concentration in an automatic cell counter (EVE™, NanoEnTek). Same number of both stromal and epithelial cells are mixed and a total of 17,000 cells are loaded in a 10X Chromium for GEM generation and barcoding, and then processed for RNA retrotranscription and library construction according to manufacturer's instructions. Finally, samples are sequenced by NGS using a Novaseq 6000 instrument

(Illumina). Figure 2 shows a scheme of the protocol of biopsy disaggregation. Table 1 summarizes the collection of biopsies that have already completed the whole scRNAseq pipeline.

Figure 2. Endometrial sample processing and single cell analysis.

Biopsy type	Number of Samples
Healthy endometrial biopsies from Estonia	
Early Proliferative	N = 11 samples
Late Proliferative	N = 4 samples
Early secretory	N = 5 samples
Mid secretory	N = 8 samples
Late secretory	N = 7 samples
Endometrial biopsies from Spain	
Healthy	N = 3 samples
Severe preeclampsia	N = 7 samples

Table 1. Characteristics of samples available to study for Deliverable 4.3

Single cell RNAseq sequencing and bioinformatic QC pipeline

10x Genomics Chromium library preparation and sequencing

The 10x-Genomics v3 libraries were prepared following the manufacturer's instructions. Libraries were sequenced, aiming at a minimum coverage of 50,000 raw reads per cell, on an Illumina NovaSeq machine (paired-end; read 1: 26 cycles; i7 index: 8 cycles, i5 index: 0 cycles; read 2: 98 cycles).

Alignment, quantification and quality control of 10X scRNA-seq

Demultiplexing of the samples were conducted using CellRanger (version 3.1.0) with the mkfastq wrapper command of Illumina. The libraries were mapped against GRCh38-3.0.0 genome reference provided by 10x Genomics. Raw gene expression matrices were computed per each scRNAseq sample using the standard pipeline counts from CellRanger software suite.

QC filtering of cells and doublet detection

Low quality cells in the samples were filtered out using the distribution of three metrics: (i) detected number of genes, (ii) detected number of counts, and (iii) mitochondrial expression ratio. Cells that have 1 median absolute deviation (MAD) in at least two of these metrics were filtered out from the sample. These quality control analyses were performed with in house made scripts in R (version 4.1).

Doublet detection was performed with DoubletFinder (2.0.3) and scds (1.6.0) R packages¹²⁻¹³. [McGinnis et al 2019; Bais et al. 2020]. Expected doublet formation rate was fixed for each sample according to the cells recovered by CellRanger. We used the hybrid approach from scds package to avoid removing false-positive doublets. Cells identified as doublets by both algorithms were removed from the samples.

Integration of data across different batches and clustering

Count matrices were further integrated and clustered using functions provided in the Seurat (4.0.1) package¹⁴⁻¹⁵. Thus, we applied SCTransform protocol based on regularized negative binomial regression¹⁶. This way it is possible to identify cross-dataset shared cell identities and perform differential expression analysis across experimental conditions between different cell types. Mitochondrial and ribosomal ratios were regressed out. We used SelectIntegrationFeatures to select variable genes for dimension reduction and downstream integration samples. We used the 4000 most variable genes. We applied PrepSCTIntegration and FindIntegrationAnchors to identify the anchors across the dataset to perform the integration step with IntegrateData with the normalization method set to SCT. In the dimensional reduction step, we used first 30 dimensions of PCA, and generated the graphical UMAP manifold to visualize the dataset with a cluster resolution of 0.8 to detect the different groups of cells present in the dataset.

Annotation of scRNA-seq datasets

Cell type identification was conducted with the examination of the specific cell markers of each cluster in the dataset. We used FindAllMarkers with the Wilcoxon Rank Sum test and adjusted the p-values with the false discovery rate (FDR) method.

Next, we classified different cell identities using canonical cell markers such as LUM, DCN and COL3A1 for the endometrial stromal cell populations; VWF gene for the identification of endothelial cells; RGS5 for perivascular population; EPCAM for epithelial cells; LYZ for the identification of macrophages cells; TPP3 for the ciliated epithelium cells; AIF1 as gene marker of dendritic cells, TOP2 and MKI67 as genes related to cell cycle; and CCL5 and CD69 as biomarkers for lymphocytes¹⁷⁻¹⁸.

Before and after full dataset integration, every sequencing run batch has been explored cluster by cluster to check that all cell types annotated were biologically meaningful, checking that their expressed gene markers were not overlapped between clusters, and that average counts of genes detected were not at lowest levels.

5 Preliminary results

5.1. Healthy endometrial Biopsies from Estonia:

We have generated scRNA-seq data from 38 endometrial biopsy samples distributed along the menstrual cycle (Table 2). We sequenced 205,251 cells, from which 100,837 resulted high quality cells used in final clustering analyses. The QC metrics for these samples confirmed a good record of quality values (Figure 3), with mitochondrial ratio always lower than 25% and number of genes detected higher than 750.

sample_id	n_cells_10x	n_cells_hq	DayCycle	ClassicPhaseCycle	PhaseCycle_by_scRNAseq
run_count_0107_HUT-21E0006_EST-09-G2-EP042	296	198	17	ES	2
run_count_0107_HUT-21E0007_EST-09-G2-ST043	1416	450	17	ES	2
run_count_0107_HUT-21E0008_EST-13-G2-EPST049	6587	5034	4	EP	1
run_count_0120_HUT-21F0007_EST-10-G2-EP44	3188	2087	8	EP	1
run_count_0120_HUT-21F0008_EST-10-G2-ST45	6354	4127	8	EP	1
run_count_0120_HUT-21F0009_EST-11-G2-ST47	4014	3144	20	MS	2
run_count_0120_HUT-21F0011_EST-11-G2-EP46	888	644	20	MS	2
run_count_0120_HUT-21F0013_EST-17-G2-EPST61	3487	1991	19	MS	2
run_count_0120_HUT-21M0001_EST-15-G2-EPST59	2701	813	12	LP	1
run_count_0156_HUT-21A0004_EST-16-G2-EPST60	6107	3014	6	EP	1
run_count_0156_HUT-21A0005_EST-18-G2-EPST62	2451	1089	18	ES	2
run_count_0156_HUT-21A0006_SPA1-19-G2-EPST63	6841	4710	26	LS	4
run_count_0156_HUT-21A0007_EST-21-G2-EPST65	5338	3897	23	MS	3
run_count_0156_HUT-21A0008_EST-22-G2-EPST66	2196	1308	18	ES	2
run_count_0156_HUT-21A0009_EST-23-G2-EPST67	5942	3315	30	LS	4
run_count_0156_HUT-21A0010_SPA1-25-G2-EPST77	10605	7459	27	LS	4
run_count_0184_HUT-21L0002_EST-26-G2-EPST78	8307	4521	7	EP	1
run_count_0184_HUT-21L0004_EST-27-G2-EPST79	2848	51	7	EP	1
run_count_0184_HUT-21L0005_EST-29-G2-EPST81	6914	4444	23	MS	3
run_count_0184_HUT-21L0006_EST-30-G2-EPST82	3886	977	12	LP	1
run_count_0184_HUT-21L0007_EST-31-G2-EPST83	9792	5386	24	LS	3
run_count_0184_HUT-21L0008_EST-32-G2-EPST84	1033	478	23	MS	3
run_count_0184_HUT-21L0009_EST-33-G2-EPST85	5579	1778	21	MS	3
run_count_0184_HUT-21L0021_EST-37-G2-EPST105	9549	7252	25	LS	4
run_count_0184_HUT-21L0022_EST-38-G2-ST106	2070	34	27	LS	4
run_count_0192_ASH-21G0011_EST-41-G2-EPST109	5947	3203	24	LS	3
run_count_0210_HUT-21O0001_EST-44-G2-EPST112	4549	3444	10	EP	1
run_count_0210_HUT-21O0005_EST-46-G2-EPST122	10566	593	13	EP	1
run_count_0210_HUT-21O0011_EST-50-G2-ST143	9891	291	10	EP	1
run_count_0029_HUT-21O0012_EST-42-G2-EPST110	18325	10386	18	ES	2
run_count_0029_HUT-21O0013_EST-43-G2-EPST111	5454	2090	19	MS	2
run_count_0234_HUT-21D0009_EST-58-G2-EPST189	3856	170	NA	NA	NA
run_count_0237_HU2-21D0037_SPA1-60-G2-EPST191	4425	642	NA	NA	NA
run_0076_HUT-20N0001_EP023	733	575	14	LP	1
run_0076_HUT-20N0002_ST024	7455	4996	14	LP	1
run_0076_HUT-20N0003_EP025	3125	1847	7	EP	1
run_0076_HUT-20N0004_ST026	9342	4596	7	EP	1

Table 2. Registered collection of biopsies from healthy women, and already analysed by scRNAseq.

Figure 3. QC metrics of scRNAseq endometrium samples. nCount refers to UMI counts. nFeature refers to number of genes, mito- and rib-o ratios refer to mitochondrial and ribosomal expression ratios respectively.

Based on the published single cell transcriptomic mapping of the progression of menstrual cycle (Wang et al 2020), four states of progression were defined for epithelium and stroma. The integrated UMAP based on Lovain distances shows clear evidence of these menstrual cycle cellular states (Figure 4), without effects from sequencing batches. Specific marker genes are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. UMAP of cell clusters and cell states identified at different menstrual cycle phases. (Left panel) Main manifold for single cell RNAseq data coloured by sequencing run. (Right panel) Main manifold for single cell RNAseq data depicting 9 endometrial cell types (epithelium, ciliated epithelium, stroma, endothelium, perivascular, myofibroblasts, macrophages, lymphocytes and erythrocytes) and 4 cellular states of epithelium and stroma based on progression of menstrual cycle (Epi_1, Epi_2, Epi_3, Epi_4, Stromal_1, Stromal_2, Stromal_3, Stromal_4).

Figure 5. DE marker genes of endometrial cell types and cell states associated to menstrual cycle progression.

We reached a good cell number coverage of all the phases of the menstrual cycle as shown in Figure 6 (by day) and Figure 7 (by phase). The total yields are: 36,932 cells in phase1; 21,279 in phase 2; 19,171 cells in phase 3; and 22,649 cells in phase 4. The evolution of cellular states along the menstrual cycle is manifested in percentages along the bars of the figures, as the day of menstrual cycle is progressing.

Figure 6. Number of cells covering each menstrual cycle day (MC-day). Barplots in percentage of cells, and cell absolute numbers.

Figure 7. Cells types and states covering each menstrual cycle phase. Barplots in percentage of cells, and cell absolute numbers.

Cloud based storage of data

Sequencing data of endometrial biopsies from healthy and preeclampsia donors has been stored in the HUTER platform, as described in deliverables D2.1 and D2.3. Access tools and viewer tools are also up and running in the platform.

5.2. Healthy and severe preeclampsia endometrial biopsies from Spain:

From the endometrial biopsies collected during the late secretory phase and processed, we have preliminar bioinformatic results of 3 healthy women and 7 women who suffered preeclampsia. Once the tissue is collected it starts the enzymatic biopsy dissociation with is developed in two stages, firstly with collagenase to obtain the stromal fraction and after that we use trypsin to obtain the epithelial fractions of individualized cells. Isolated cells are analyzed by single cell using chromium 10X technologies. Cells pass through a channel and every single cell is added a specific barcode and each cell with each barcode are encapsulated in an oil gem. After that single cell gems are collected, retrotranscription is made to obtain cDNA and the oil of gems is removed. At this point cDNA is ready to sequence. After sequencing, data are download using Cell Ranger.

Then data pass a quality control where cells that has less than 750 detected genes are removed and cells with more than 25% of mitochondrial genes are also removed (Table 3).

	Number of patients	Total number of cells analyzed
Healthy	3	11511
Severe Preeclampsia	7	36455
TOTAL	10	47966

Table 3. Numbers of patients and total cells analyzed after the quality filter application.

Once samples are normalized it starts the annotation process, in this case we use Wang, et al. 2020 database¹⁸ because the published the single-cell composition of the endometrium and combine manual annotation (Figure 8). Preliminary results show that comparing cell type distribution between a healthy situation and women who suffered preeclampsia previously, one population between stromal and epithelial is reduced in control cases and increased in Preeclampsia.

Figure 8. (A) Cell type identify of the endometrial biopsies collected from healthy (HE) and preeclamptic (PE) patients. (B) Overlapping of identify cells between healthy and preeclamptic cellular atlas.

We perform next subsequent bioinformatic analysis based on differential expression analysis revealing different pattern of expression comparing the two situations (Figure 9). In general, there is a Downregulation of genes in sPE condition. Going deeply into some DEGs, for example, Phospholipase Cy2 (PLCG2). PLCG2 is downregulated in PE in every cell type except NKs.

Figure 9. Differential expression analysis in single-cell cell-types.

The gene enrichment analysis shows different pathways altered in preeclampsia samples represented in blue compared to healthy represented in red (Figure 10). In endothelial cells mitochondrial pathways are affected in preeclampsia. In epithelial cells genes related with the immune system and cell differentiation are upregulated in PE. And in Perivascular pathways interleukin and leucocyte cell adhesion are also upregulate in PE samples reinforcing the imbalance of immune system in PE compared to control.

Figure 10. Gene enrichment analysis of healthy (HE) and preeclamptic (PE) samples.

6 Public dissemination and conclusions

Although no publications have been generated to date, INCLIVA researchers will present in SRI meeting. SRI, the Society for Reproductive Investigation holds its 69th Annual Scientific Meeting this year in Denver on March 15th-19th 2022. The event counts with a session on preeclampsia March 18th, where Dr. Tamara Garrido & PhD student Irene Muñoz and team will participate with the abstract titled **“Single-cell atlas of defective decidualization in preeclampsia reveals different endometrial cell composition”**, which was selected for an oral presentation in a concurrent oral session.

In addition, to highlight the results and the work performed, reserachers from INCLIVA participated in all relevant HCA Network and Annual meetings showing all relevant information, specifically at:

- HCA-EC Consortia update meeting, EC-HCA virtual meeting held on September 22nd 2020.
- HCA-EC Consortia update meeting, EC-HCA virtual meeting held on November 9th 2021.
- HCA General Meeting United Kingdom and Europe Townhall, June 15th 2021
- Human Cell Atlas General Virtual Meeting, June 28th - 30th 2021.

In order to adjust HUTER data platform to HCA metadata format standards, we have maintained fluid communication meetings with Data Portal and Data Wrangler teams from HCA-DCP.

With regards to interacting with non-academic stakeholders and the general public, INCLIVA team participated in the Midnight event in September 24th 2021 at the European Corner in collaboration with Europe Direct, presenting both an informative poster and an activity stand.

In conclusion, bearing in mind the goals from Work Package 4:

- (v) Identification of cell types and states in the endometrium, across life span for a healthy uterus.
- (vi) Elucidation of the effects of the menstrual cycle on the endometrial cells of fertile women.
- (vii) Identification of cell types and states in the preeclampsia case study.
- (viii) Elucidation of the identification of potential molecular mechanisms underlying the endometrial pathogenesis in sPE.

We can indicate that with the actions performed in Deliverable D4.3 despite the COVID-19 pandemic hugely affecting the number of donors recruited on the project and the shortage of samples during the first part of the project we have successfully analyzed more than 48 samples and 250.000 cells.

Based on our experience, we are confident that by the end of period granted (June 2022) we will reach the pursued goals.

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